

STUDIES ON THE FORMATION OF ALUMINATES

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Aluminates of Ba, Sr, Mg, Zn and Ni have been prepared at high temperatures.

Tanaka (*Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1941, 16, 186) obtained $MgO \cdot Al_2O_3$ by heating a mixture of MgO and Al_2O_3 at 1400° for 10 hours. Noguchi (*J. Japan Ceram. Assoc.*, 1948, 56, 77) also obtained the same compound by heating equimolar mixtures of MgO and Al_2O_3 at 1900° , using a large number of mineralisers.

Mourelou (*Rev. gen. Sci.*, 1915, 26, 399) synthesised zinc aluminate by heating a mixture of zinc oxide, alumina and boric oxide. Meunier (*Bull. Soc. Min.*, 1887, 10, 194) prepared zinc aluminate by heating to bright redness a mixture of alumina, zinc oxide, cryolite and aluminium chloride, and Deville and Caron (*Compt. rend.*, 1858, 46, 764) by vaporising a mixture of zinc and aluminium fluorides in the presence of boric oxide.

Jander and Grob (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1940, 246, 67), Milligan and Merten (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1946, 50, 465) and Chaumeton, Bilde and Devaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1951, 232, 1556) prepared $NiO \cdot Al_2O_3$ by heating the mixtures of corresponding oxides at various temperatures.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of barium aluminates by the interaction of bauxite and barytes, $Ba(OH)_2$ or $Ba(NO_3)_2$, and strontium aluminates by the interaction of bauxite and strontium sulphate or strontium nitrate at high temperatures. The work was further extended to the preparation of aluminates of Mg, Zn and Ni.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All the chemicals used were of Merck E.P. quality. The bauxite used was from Katni and on analysis furnished the composition recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	Expt. No. 1.	Expt. No. 2.	Average.
Moisture	1.51%	1.52%	1.515%
Combined water	28.54	28.52	28.53
SiO ₂	7.28	7.26	7.27
(TiO ₂ & Fe ₂ O ₃)	8.00	8.06	8.03
Al ₂ O ₃	54.40	54.30	54.35

Several mixtures were prepared by weighing out accurately bauxite and other constituents in different proportions. They were mixed in an agate pestle and mortar, transferred into the crucibles and heated at high temperatures for different intervals of time. Duplicate experiments were carried out in each case. The heated mass was taken out, powdered well and weighed. A known weight of this mixture

was taken for analysis. It was first extracted with water and afterwards with dilute HCl, and the quantities of Al_2O_3 , BaO or SrO were estimated in both the extracts separately. In experiments where bauxite was heated with $Ba(NO_3)_2$, $Ba(OH)_2$ or $Sr(NO_3)_2$, the water extract was not analysed.

TABLE IIA

Barium aluminate.
Time of heating = 5 hours.

Expt. No.	Bauxite: barytes	Temp.	Water-soluble (BaO).	Dil. HCl-soluble.		Compound.
				BaO.	Al_2O_3 .	
1	10: 15	1400°-1450°	...	6.524 g.	1.452 g.	3 BaO. Al_2O_3
2	10: 15	"		6.551	1.460	3 BaO. Al_2O_3
3	10: 50	"	7.128 g	14.528	4.806	2 BaO. Al_2O_3
4	10: 50	"	7.166	14.523	4.802	"
5	10: 25	1200°-1250°	5.653	11.464	3.812	"
6	10: 25	"	5.652	11.448	3.803	"
7	10: 40	"	3.624	7.286	2.422	"
8	10: 40	"	3.628	7.274	2.421	"

TABLE IIB

Time of heating = 2.5 hours. Temp. = 1000°-1050°

Expt. No.	Bauxite.	$Ba(NO_3)_2$.	Dil. HCl-soluble.		Compound.
			BaO.	Al_2O_3 .	
9	1.0 g.	3.5 g.	0.530 g.	0.176 g.	2 BaO. Al_2O_3
10	1.0	3.5 $Ba(OH)_2.8H_2O$.	0.532	0.177	"
11	1.0	4.0	1.180	0.393	2 BaO. Al_2O_3
12	1.0	4.0	1.178	0.392	"

TABLE IIIA

Strontium aluminate.
Time of heating = 5 hours.

Expt. No.	Bauxite: $Sr(SO_4)$.	Temp.	Water-soluble.	Dil. HCl-soluble.		Compound.
				SrO.	Al_2O_3 .	
13	10: 15	1400°-1450°	...	5.080 g.	2.520 g.	2 SrO. Al_2O_3
14	10: 15	"	...	5.110	2.522	"
15	10: 20	"	...	5.478	2.710	"
16	10: 20	"	...	5.490	2.712	"
17	10: 25	"	...	8.362	4.120	"
18	10: 25	"	...	8.358	4.118	"
19	10: 40	"	...	9.124	4.556	"
20	10: 40	"	...	9.126	4.554	"
21	10: 15	1200°-1250°	2.464 g.	4.028	1.316	3 SrO. Al_2O_3
22	10: 15	"	2.628	4.034	1.328	"
23	10: 40	"	3.240	6.920	2.268	"
24	10: 40	"	3.260	6.925	2.274	"

TABLE III B

Time of heating = 5 hours. Temp. = 1000°-1050°.

Expt. No.	Rauxite: Sr(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O.	Dil. HCl-soluble.		Compound.
		SrO.	Al ₂ O ₃ .	
25	10 : 40	5.140 g.	1.660 g.	3 SrO·Al ₂ O ₃
26	10 : 40	5.142	1.681	"

Magnesium and Zinc Aluminates.—Basic aluminium acetate and MgSO₄·7H₂O, MgCl₂·6H₂O or ZnSO₄·7H₂O were weighed, mixed in an agate pestle and mortar, transferred into the crucibles and heated at high temperatures. The heated mass was taken out, boiled with dilute HCl and filtered. The residue was washed with hot water, dried and weighed. A known weight of the residue was taken for analysis. It was fused with Na₂CO₃, KNO₃ and a small quantity of NaOH and the fused mass extracted with dilute HCl. It was filtered and washed with hot water. The residue was fused again with a mixture of Na₂CO₃, KNO₃ and NaOH, and the process repeated till the whole mass was extracted with dilute HCl. The quantities of Al₂O₃ and MgO or ZnO were estimated in both the extracts separately.

TABLE IV

Magnesium aluminate.

Time of heating = 2 hours. Basic Al acetate taken = 3.0 g.

Expt. No.	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O.	Temp.	Dil. HCl-soluble (MgO).	Analysis of the residue.		Compound.
				MgO.	Al ₂ O ₃ .	
27	3.06 g.	1400°	Negligible	0.4980 g.	1.2740 g.	MgO·Al ₂ O ₃
28	3.06	"	"	0.4978	1.2746	"
29	5.12	"	0.5070 g.	0.4920	1.2702	"
30	6.12	"	0.5072	0.4914	1.2700	"
	MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O.					
31	2.6	1200°	Negligible	0.4976	1.2724	"
32	2.6	"	"	0.4964	1.2730	"
33	5.2	"	0.4984 g.	0.5002	1.2746	"
34	5.2	"	0.4992	0.4996	1.2742	"

TABLE V

Zinc aluminate.

Time of heating = 2 hours. Temp. = 1200°. Basic Al acetate taken = 2.95 g.

Expt. No.	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O.	Dil. HCl-soluble (ZnO).	Analysis of the residue.		Compound.
			ZnO.	Al ₂ O ₃ .	
35	3.53 g.	...	0.992 g.	1.240 g.	ZnO·Al ₂ O ₃
36	3.53	...	0.988	1.241	"
37	7.06	0.995 g.	1.002	1.251	"
38	7.06	1.002	1.001	1.253	"

Nickel Aluminate.—Basic aluminium acetate and nickel acetate (hydrated) were weighed accurately, mixed in an agate pestle and mortar and transferred into the crucible and heated at high temperatures. The heated mass was taken out and extracted with dilute HCl (2-3*N*). The residue was boiled with HCl (10 *N*), filtered, washed with hot water and analysed. The quantities of Al_2O_3 and NiO were estimated in HCl (conc.) extract.

TABLE VI

Nickel aluminate.

Time of heating = 2 hours. Temp. = 1200°. Basic Al acetate taken = 3.30 g.

Expt. No.	Ni-acetate.	Dil HCl-soluble (NiO).	Conc. HCl-soluble. NiO.	Al_2O_3 .	Compound.
39	2.37 g.	0.408 g.	0.316 g.	0.430 g.	$NiO.Al_2O_3$
40	2.37	0.412	0.311	0.426	"
41	4.74	1.042	0.413	0.562	"
42	4.74	1.046	0.411	0.563	"

DISCUSSION

Barium Aluminate.—It is evident from Table 11A that in all the cases the water extract provides sufficient quantities of BaO, but not even traces of $Al(OH)_3$, and the acid extract affords BaO as well as $Al(OH)_3$. As alumina present in the bauxite was heated at very high temperatures, which would render it insoluble in dilute or concentrated HCl, barium aluminates must have been formed from which alumina had been extracted by dilute acid.

In expts. No. 1 and 2, where the mixture containing bauxite and barytes in the ratio of 10:15 was heated at 1400°-1450°, the mass was glass-like and could be taken out of the crucible with difficulty. When boiled with water for a long time it did not disintegrate and the water extract neither responded to the test for $Ba(OH)_2$, nor for $Al(OH)_3$; when boiled with dilute HCl it, however, disintegrated. The ratio of BaO to Al_2O_3 obtained in the acid extract indicates the compound as $3BaO.Al_2O_3$. When the above experiments were repeated with larger quantities of barytes, the mass was not so hard and it disintegrated when boiled with water; the water extract provided sufficient quantities of BaO but no Al_2O_3 . The ratio of BaO to Al_2O_3 in the acid extract indicates the composition of the compound as $2BaO.Al_2O_3$. If BaO in the water extracts be added to BaO in the acid extract, the compound formed would correspond to $3BaO.Al_2O_3$.

Expts. No. 5 and 6 show that only $Ba(OH)_2$ is obtained in the water extracts and both $Ba(OH)_2$ and $Al(OH)_3$ in the acid extracts. From the ratio of BaO to Al_2O_3 in the acid extract the compound appears to be $2BaO.Al_2O_3$. If BaO from the water and the acid extracts be added together, the ratio BaO to Al_2O_3 will correspond to $3BaO.Al_2O_3$.

The above experiments show that the compound formed is $3BaO.Al_2O_3$ in all the cases which, when treated with water, hydrolyses to $Ba(OH)_2$ and $2BaO.Al_2O_3$; when bauxite is heated with $Ba(OH)_2$ or $Ba(NO_3)_2$, the ratio of BaO to Al_2O_3 in the acid extract indicates the compound as $2BaO.Al_2O_3$.

Strontium Aluminates.—Expts. No. 13-20, carried out at 1400°-1450°, show that $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ is not obtained in the water extract. The ratio of SrO to Al_2O_3 in the acid extract shows the compound to be $2\text{SrO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

Expts. No. 21-24, carried out at 1200°-1250°, afforded enough quantities of $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ with water. From the ratio of SrO to Al_2O_3 in the acid extract the compound appears to be $3\text{SrO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. Bauxite when heated with $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ at 1000°-1050° furnished the same compound, $3\text{SrO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

From these results it is definitely established that $3\text{SrO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is formed at 1200°-1250° and $2\text{SrO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ at 1400°-1450°.

Magnesium Aluminate.—From Table IV it is evident that the compound formed by heating a mixture of MgSO_4 , $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and basic aluminium acetate at 1400° is $\text{MgO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, which is insoluble in water and in HCl (dil. and conc.). Expts. No. 29 and 30 were carried out with double the quantity of magnesium sulphate but the same compound was formed and unchanged MgO was extracted with HCl. The experiment, when repeated with $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixed with NaCl instead of MgSO_4 , $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, furnished the same compound. In this case the reaction occurred at a much lower temperature and was over in a shorter duration.

Zinc Aluminate.—In expts. No. 35 and 36, when the molar ratio of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and aluminium acetate was 1:1, neither Al_2O_3 nor ZnO was obtained in the acid extract. Expts. No. 37 and 38 were carried out with double the quantity of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the fused mass, when extracted with HCl (conc.) gave a large amount of ZnO, but no Al_2O_3 . The residue on analysis furnished the compound, $\text{ZnO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

Nickel Aluminate.—Expts. No. 39 and 40 show that the only aluminate which is formed by heating calculated quantities of nickel and aluminium acetates corresponding to mono- and di-nickel aluminates at about 1200° is $\text{NiO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. When double the quantity of nickel acetate is used, no dinickel aluminate is formed. The unchanged NiO was extracted with dilute HCl, and the ignited Al_2O_3 left as insoluble residue.

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